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AUDIT COMMITTEE SIZE AND SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING OF LISTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA: MODERATED BY WOMEN CHAIRPERSON

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ABSTRACT

The quality of sustainability reporting has become a critical issue for organizations, especially the banking sector, as stakeholder demand greater transparency on environmental, social and governance factors. Despite growing attention, many firms, particularly in developing economies like Nigeria, face challenges in ensuring robust sustainability disclosures. This study examines the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting and the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson of deposit money banks in Nigeria over a 15-year period (2010–2024). A total of 14 banks were selected using census sampling technique from the total deposit money banks operating in Nigeria, based on the availability of audited annual reports for the entire study period. The study employed an ex-post facto research design using multiple regression to analyze the data. Results show that audit committee size significantly affects sustainability reporting, indicating that larger committees provide more effective oversight of non-financial disclosures. However, the study found that

the audit committee women chairperson does not significantly affect sustainability reporting nor does it moderate the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting. The study concludes that while gender diversity within the audit committee is beneficial for overall governance, the role of women as chairpersons does not enhance the effectiveness of sustainability reporting in deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study recommends that deposit money banks in Nigeria should focus on increasing audit committee size by including members with strong background in sustainability reporting. It also recommends that banks should continue to encourage gender diversity within the audit committee, but without overemphasizing the role of women chairperson.

KEYWORDS: Audit Committee Size, Audit Committee Women Chairperson, Sustainability Reporting, Bank Size, Deposit Money Banks, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability reporting refers to the process by which organizations disclose information regarding their economic, environmental, and social impacts, governance practices, and the steps they take to operate responsibly and sustainably. In the context of deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria, sustainability reporting is gaining increasing importance as stakeholders demand greater accountability from organizations regarding their environmental and social practices, as well as their long-term viability. The practice of sustainability reporting has evolved significantly over the last few decades, driven by various forces including stakeholder expectations, global regulatory frameworks, and a growing awareness of corporate responsibility (Gupta & Sharma 2020). Traditionally, sustainability reporting focused primarily on environmental issues, but today, KPMG, (2020) indicates that it encompasses a broad range of topics, including corporate social responsibility (CSR), governance, stakeholder engagement, and long-term value creation. This shift reflects a growing recognition that businesses must go beyond financial performance and address the broader impact of their activities on society and the environment (Eccles & Krzus, 2018).

An audit committee (AC) is a critical component of corporate governance, especially within financial institutions such as Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). It serves as a safeguard for the integrity and transparency of financial reporting, internal controls, and compliance with legal and regulatory requirements. In recent years, the role of audit committees has expanded beyond traditional financial oversight to include non-financial aspects of corporate governance, such as sustainability reporting. In the realm of sustainability reporting, Zheng & Li, (2021) averred that audit committees have gained increasing recognition for their role in ensuring that non-financial disclosures are aligned with established standards, maintain accuracy and uphold transparency. The characteristics of an audit committee, such as its size, independence, meeting frequency, and the financial expertise of its members, can have a significant impact on the quality and effectiveness of sustainability reporting. The size of an audit committee is one of its most studied attributes in corporate governance. Larger audit committees are often perceived as more effective due to the diversity of perspectives and expertise they bring to the table (Chou & Hsu, 2020). Studies indicates that larger audit committees are better equipped to handle the increasing demands of both financial and non-financial oversight, including sustainability reporting. A larger committee can provide more comprehensive monitoring of sustainability initiatives and ensure that these disclosures reflect the company's true environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance (Brammer & Pavelin, 2021).

Women chairperson in the audit committee has been the subject of considerable academic interest. Research has shown that gender diversity within corporate governance structures, particularly in the boardroom, has a significant effect on organizational outcomes (Nielsen & Huse, 2010). The chairperson of the audit committee plays a crucial role in shaping the priorities of the committee, setting

the agenda for meetings, and ensuring that the committee effectively oversees all areas of corporate governance, including sustainability reporting. Empirical studies suggest that female leaders tend to emphasize values such as ethical behavior, social responsibility, and long-term sustainability, which can influence the corporate governance culture within the organization (Post & Byron, 2015). In particular, a female audit committee chairperson is likely to champion more responsible corporate behavior and be more committed to ensuring that sustainability disclosures meet the expectations of stakeholders, including regulators, investors, and the public (Adams & Ferreira, 2009).

The banking sector in Nigeria, particularly Deposit Money Banks (DMBs), plays a central role in the nation's economy by driving financial intermediation, facilitating trade and supporting economic growth. The financial sector has been pivotal in the Nigerian economy by fostering financial inclusion and providing credit to key sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and infrastructure, which are essential for economic development (Adeyemi & Adebisi, 2021). However, in recent years, Nigerian DMBs have faced growing scrutiny not only regarding their financial performance but also about their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices, which have become critical for long-term sustainability (Adegbite & Owolabi, 2021). Despite regulatory frameworks designed to promote sustainability in banking, such as the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) sustainability guidelines and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) ESG disclosures, the quality, consistency, and reliability of sustainability reporting in Nigerian DMBs remain a significant concern (Ogundipe et al., 2020; Adeyemi, 2022). This issue has profound implications for the credibility of the banking sector, the trust of stakeholders, and the sector's alignment with global sustainability standards (Alalade & Ogboi, 2024).

Audit committees play a pivotal role in addressing these issues by overseeing and ensuring the credibility of both financial and non-financial disclosures, including sustainability reports (Oyerogba & Oladele, 2024). However, recent empirical evidence on how certain audit committee characteristics such as its size affect the quality of sustainability reporting in Nigerian banks are limited (Soyemi et al., 2024). This lack of insight raises questions about the role and effectiveness of audit committees in ensuring that banks meet the growing expectations for transparent and comprehensive sustainability disclosures (Alalade & Ogboi, 2024). Moreover, the increasing focus on gender diversity within corporate governance, particularly the presence of women in leadership roles, has introduced an additional layer of complexity. The role of a female audit committee chairperson a relatively understudied phenomenon in Nigerian banking may have a moderating influence on the effectiveness of audit committees.

The main objective of this study therefore is to examine the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting, moderated by audit committee women chairperson of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives include to;

- i. Investigate the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- ii. Analyse the effect of audit committee women chairperson on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
- iii. Assess the effect of the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson on audit committee size and sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

The following hypotheses was tested in null form;

H₀₁: Audit committee size has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Audit committee women chairperson has no significant effect on sustainability reporting of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate audit committee size and sustainability reporting of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria

This study holds significant value for practitioners, particularly managers, auditors, and policymakers within the Nigerian banking industry. By providing empirical evidence on how audit committee size influence sustainability reporting, it equips practitioners with insights into governance mechanisms that enhance transparency and accountability. For the government and regulatory agencies, this study provides valuable guidance in formulating and reviewing policies related to corporate governance and sustainability disclosures. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) can utilize these insights to refine existing sustainability guidelines and audit committee regulations. From the perspective of the society at large, this study underscores the importance of transparent sustainability reporting as a means of ensuring that financial institutions operate responsibly and contribute to sustainable development. Finally, for employees, this study highlights how a strong commitment to sustainability reporting often translates into better organizational reputation and employee engagement. Employees benefit from working within institutions that prioritize transparency and sustainability, thereby fostering motivation, trust, and long-term job satisfaction.

The scope of this study is designed to analyze the effect of audit committee size on the sustainability reporting disclosure of Nigerian deposit money banks (DMBs). In addition, the study investigates the moderating role of a female audit committee chairperson in influencing the effectiveness of audit committee size in overseeing sustainability reporting over a 15-year period (from 2010 to 2024). This period is chosen for its relevance in understanding key transformations that have shaped the Nigerian banking industry in terms of governance reforms, sustainability reporting, and the role of gender diversity in leadership positions within corporate structures. The study also aims to explore whether the presence of a female chairperson in the audit committee moderates the relationship between the committee's size and the sustainability reporting disclosure.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

The conceptual framework of sustainability reporting provides the structure and concept for understanding the role, importance, and dimensions of sustainability disclosures in organizations. Sustainability reporting refers to the process by which organizations disclose information about their environmental, social, and governance (ESG) performance and how their activities impact society and the environment. Gupta and Sharma (2020) defines sustainability reporting as the “disclosure of information on environmental, social, and economic performance by organizations, aimed at demonstrating the organization’s accountability to stakeholders regarding its impact on society.” Gupta and Sharma’s definition emphasizes the broad scope of sustainability reporting, which not only includes environmental factors but also the social and economic impacts of an organization’s operations.

Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) (2016) provides a widely adopted framework for sustainability reporting and defines it as “the practice of measuring, disclosing, and being accountable to internal and external stakeholders for organizational performance toward the goal of sustainable development.” The GRI’s definition highlights the importance of transparency, accountability, and the need for organizations to disclose their performance in a way that is accessible and relevant to various stakeholders. Eccles and Krzus (2018) argue that sustainability reporting is “a form of integrated

reporting that seeks to provide a comprehensive picture of the organization's ability to create value in the long term, considering not just financial capital but also human, intellectual, social, and environmental capitals." This definition reflects the integrated nature of sustainability reporting, wherein non-financial aspects are linked with financial performance to give stakeholders a more complete understanding of an organization's sustainability.

The aforementioned concepts from previous studies only emphasised on social and environmental reporting while ignoring governance and economic disclosure. Furthermore, voluntary disclosure and transparency are not given nearly as much weight as regulatory compliance. It is for this reason that this study defines sustainability reporting disclosure as the process of disclosing through open, accessible reports an organization's governance, environmental, social, and economic performance as well as its progress towards sustainability goals. Transparency, accountability, and trust among stakeholders are fostered by disclosure in sustainability reporting, which facilitates informed decision-making and advances sustainable development.

Audit committee is described as a sub-committee of the board of directors whose main responsibilities are overseeing the financial reporting process, internal controls, risk management, and compliance functions within the organization, ensuring that all the financial and non-financial disclosures meet appropriate standards according to Hermanson and Hurley (2024). This definition highlights the expanding role of audit committees in overseeing both financial and non-financial reporting, including sustainability disclosures. Moustafa et al. (2021) defined the audit committee as "a governance body with the responsibility for overseeing the financial integrity of the company, auditing processes, and the overall effectiveness of corporate governance, with a growing role in monitoring non-financial disclosures such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental reports." This definition emphasizes the inclusion of non-financial reporting, reflecting modern shifts in governance oversight. These definitions from earlier academics have mostly concentrated on the audit committee's role in financial reporting, overlooking other growing issues like sustainability and environmental risks. Also prior definitions have been constructed with a western or developed-country perspective, restricting their application in various cultural and economic context in developing economies like Nigeria. Consequently, this study considered audit committee as a sub-committee of the board of directors mandated to assess the organisation's financial and non-financial reporting; internal control, risk management, and audit.

Audit committee size as defined by Lopez-Iturriaga and Zarza-Herranz (2020) is the number of members in the audit committee, with an optimal size being one that balances efficiency and expertise in monitoring financial reports and overseeing governance. Larger committees may provide broader perspectives, but they may also face challenges with coordination and decision-making. This definition underscores the importance of finding an optimal size for the audit committee, which ensures that diverse expertise is available while minimizing inefficiencies. Al-Okaily and Naueihed (2020) defined the audit committee size as "the total number of members constituting the audit committee, with studies suggesting that an ideal size allows the committee to leverage diverse expertise and ensure effective monitoring of financial and non-financial reporting, including sustainability disclosures." They note that, typically, the average size is about 3.62 members, which is found to enhance effectiveness without becoming too large to manage efficiently.

This study defines audit committee size as the number of members serving on the audit committee of a corporation, which directly impacts its ability to provide effective oversight over financial reporting, internal controls, and risk management processes. The size of the audit committee influences the range of expertise and perspectives available for decision-making, but the committee's effectiveness is contingent upon achieving a balance between having enough members to cover various skills and

maintaining efficient coordination and communication. This definition recognizes the importance of size not just for the sake of diversity in perspective, but for practical governance concerns, such as ensuring that the committee functions smoothly and is able to fulfill its responsibilities effectively.

The audit committee women chairperson refers to a female director who serves as the head of an organization's audit committee. This role combines the traditional responsibilities of an audit committee chair such as overseeing financial reporting, internal controls, risk management, and compliance with the distinct leadership influence and ethical orientation often associated with female leadership. Over the last decade, and especially in recent years (2020–2024), there has been growing scholarly interest in how the gender of audit committee chairs impacts governance outcomes, including sustainability reporting, transparency, and firm performance. Hossain, et al. (2022) defined a female audit committee chairperson as “a woman appointed to lead the audit committee, bringing distinct oversight styles, governance sensibilities, and ethical perspectives that influence both financial and non-financial reporting.” The study argued that female chairs tend to enforce more diligent oversight, leading to improved disclosure quality and stakeholder trust. Moustafa et al. (2021) described the role of a female audit committee chairperson as critical for introducing “diversity of thought, increased scrutiny, and higher ethical orientation” in governance processes. Their findings show that women in chair positions are associated with lower incidences of corporate scandals and more transparent disclosures, especially in sensitive reporting areas such as environmental and social impact.

This study defines audit committee women chairperson as a female director appointed to lead the audit committee, who plays a pivotal role in overseeing the organization's financial and non-financial reporting, internal controls, and compliance mechanisms—while bringing a distinctive leadership style grounded in ethical judgment, stakeholder sensitivity, and diverse perspectives. By viewing the female audit committee chair not just as a demographic marker, but as a governance catalyst, this definition captures the strategic, ethical, and oversight dimensions of her leadership. It affirms that the value she brings isn't just in “being a woman,” but in how she leads with integrity, prudence, and accountability. Incorporating bank size as a control variable is crucial for understanding its influence on sustainability reporting practices in Nigerian deposit money banks (DMBs). Bank size is often considered a significant determinant of corporate governance structures, including the audit committee, and is likely to affect the extent to which sustainability disclosures are made. Bank size can influence the audit committee's ability to oversee sustainability reporting. Larger banks typically have more resources, including financial, human, and technological capital, to adopt and report on sustainable practices (Tschopp & Nastanski, 2014; Jensen, 2019). These banks are also under greater scrutiny from investors, regulators, and stakeholders, which incentivizes more robust sustainability disclosures (Wang & Li, 2019). Larger banks tend to be more proactive in aligning with global sustainability frameworks and regulations, thus ensuring that their audit committees oversee the implementation of comprehensive sustainability reporting (Dhaliwal et al., 2014). Smaller banks, on the other hand, may face resource constraints, which can limit their ability to implement advanced sustainability practices or to allocate sufficient attention to non-financial disclosures (Liu et al., 2016). The size of the bank thus affects the financial and organizational capacity to integrate Environmental, Economic, Social, and Governance (EESG) issues into corporate reporting.

The development of the theoretical framework involves an analysis of the body of research on the relationship that exist between audit committee size and sustainability reporting as moderated by women chairperson of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. This framework provided a foundation for the examination of the empirical studies that was covered in this study. As a result, this study was anchored on the Agency theory. The principal-agent relationship, or the relationship between managers and the company's owners, is provided by Jensen and Meckling (1976). According to this proposition,

the relationship is "a contract under which one or more persons i.e the principal(s) engage another person (the agent) to perform some service on their behalf which involves delegating some decision-making authority to the agent." By this proposition, the principals of a company are its shareholders, and it is the shareholders that choose managers, or agents, to run the company and generate returns on their investments. Needless to say, it can be assumed that the managers may not necessarily work to the benefit of the shareholders if they themselves are mostly concerned with gaining the maximum income in the form of bonuses, for instance (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Information asymmetry, or the owners' lack of awareness about the managers' side of the business's activities giving the managers an advantage in knowing the real state of the company, is another problem that arises naturally in agency partnerships. Increased knowledge asymmetry between principals and agents causes more complex agency difficulties (He & Luo, 2018). Because it causes inefficiencies, this might reduce the firm's overall value (Rodriguez et al. 2015). The narrow concept has drawn criticism for the theory that contends that managers are inherently self-serving and opportunistic, acting only in their own best interests. Another criticism focuses on the idea that owners and shareholders are the only significant stakeholders (Brennan & Solomon, 2008; Christopher, 2010). An objection to agency theory's inability to explain why the same justification for utility maximisation would not apply to independent auditors who are trusted by owners was put forth by Armstrong (1991), quoted in Mihret (2014). A coherent group would be beneficial for committees and that, as such, gender diversity may lead to conflict of interest because the genders may not agree (Sultana et al. 2015). Previous works have shown, for example, women are prescribing in discourses of financial personality than men are thus conflict arises due to different outlooks (Levin, et al 1993 cited in Sultana et al. 2015).

While multiple theories are relevant, Agency Theory is the most appropriate to underpin this study because firstly, this aligns directly with the committee's responsibility to oversee both financial and sustainability reporting. Secondly, sustainability reporting, while voluntary in some contexts, is increasingly becoming a means to hold management accountable to stakeholders, reinforcing agency concerns about truthful disclosure and ethical behavior.

The empirical review of literature aims to provide an in-depth understanding of the relationship between audit committee size and the moderating role of a female audit committee chairperson, and the sustainability reporting disclosure in Nigerian Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). In a recent study conducted by Meo, et al. (2024) on the influence of the board of commissioners, committees audits, and company size on sustainability reporting, Indonesia. The sample size used for the study was 63 firms and the scope of the study was from 2017-2022. The study adopted the quantitative research design and used SPSS to run a Multiple Regression Analysis. The study revealed that Audit committee size significantly and positively impacts sustainability reporting. Larger audit committees with diverse members ensure more thorough oversight of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors. This suggests that firms with larger committees may be better equipped to address complex sustainability challenges. The study focused on Indonesia; findings may differ in countries with different governance structures and regulatory frameworks.

Waseem, et al. (2024) conducted a study on impact of audit committee attributes and liquidity on sustainability reporting in Pakistan. Eighty firms were used as sample size and the study period was from 2017-2021. Regression Analysis was run using Eviews. The study showed that audit committee size and liquidity have a positive correlation with the quality of sustainability reports. Larger audit committees tend to ensure more accurate and detailed sustainability reporting. This finding highlights the significance of both audit structure and financial stability in driving effective sustainability

disclosure. The focus on liquidity as an additional factor may obscure other relevant variables such as regulatory compliance.

Subsequently, Georgesco and Neacșu (2024) conducted a study on an analysis of the relationship between audit committee characteristics and the level of assurance of the sustainability report in Romania. The study made use of 38 firms as its sample size and covered a period of 2020-2023. Quantitative research design was used and Structural Equation Modeling adopted as the methodology. The findings revealed Audit committee size was positively linked to the level of assurance provided for sustainability reports. Larger audit committees are more likely to scrutinize sustainability disclosures in greater detail, leading to enhanced credibility. This demonstrates that committee capacity can play an essential role in the reliability of sustainability information. The study's reliance on Romanian firms may limit its applicability to countries with differing regulatory environments.

Hendrati et al. (2023) conducted a study on the role of moderation activities of the audit committee and the board of directors on the planning of the sustainability report in Indonesia. 112 respondents were used as sample size and the period under study was 2021-2022. The study employed Quantitative research design, the methodology used was Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). The study revealed that audit committee size has an inverse relationship with sustainability reporting. Larger committees can sometimes complicate decision-making processes, which leads to lower quality sustainability reports. This result implies that firms may need to be cautious about increasing committee size without considering its impact on efficiency. The study however focused on a limited geographical area, which may not fully generalize to other regions with different regulatory environments.

In a similar study by Buallay and Al-Ajmi (2020) on the role of audit committee attributes in corporate sustainability reporting: Evidence from banks in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). The study made use of 76 banks and the study period was 2012-2018. The study also used Quantitative Design and Regression Analysis was run using SPSS. The study found that a positive relationship exists between audit committee size and sustainability reporting in banks. Larger committees, particularly those with diverse expertise, significantly improve the comprehensiveness of sustainability reports. This indicates that committee diversity and size may play a crucial role in ensuring robust disclosures. While the study focused on banks, it may not be generalizable to other industries, especially in countries with different regulatory frameworks.

Gatimbu et al. (2025) investigated sustainability reporting in sub-Saharan Africa: Audit committee diversity and executive compensation across 102 firms in the region. The study covered the period from 2016–2022 and applied multivariate regression using STATA. It was found that audit committees led by women chairpersons were more consistent in applying sustainability frameworks and aligning them with compensation practices. This demonstrates that gender leadership can enhance alignment between reporting and performance incentives. However, it was limited to firms listed on the stock exchange and excluded SMEs.

Similarly, Almonte (2025) conducted a study titled board characteristics in European sustainable companies: the moderating role of board gender diversity. The study focused on 80 listed companies across Europe and covered the period from 2015–2022. A panel data design was adopted and multiple regression analysis was used through STATA. The findings revealed that female audit committee chairpersons significantly improved the quality of sustainability reporting through enhanced oversight and accountability. This finding underscores the role of gender diversity at leadership levels in strengthening corporate governance and sustainability outcomes.

However, the study did not distinguish the influence of executive versus non-executive female leaders on reporting. Zampone et al. (2024) carried out a study on gender diversity and SDG

disclosure: the mediating role of the sustainability committee using data from listed European companies. The sample size and population details were not explicitly stated, but the study focused on sustainability committee dynamics. The period covered was from 2017–2022. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was used as the design and AMOS software was applied. The findings of the study showed that a female chairperson of the audit committee positively influences the strength of the sustainability committee, leading to enhanced SDG reporting practices. This result points towards the beneficial impact of gender-diverse leadership on sustainability committee effectiveness. However, the study focused only on SDG-related disclosures, limiting its applicability to broader ESG reporting.

Abu Alia et al. (2024) examined the study titled can effective boards drive environmental innovation? The moderating power of CSR committees using a sample of 95 manufacturing firms in the MENA region. The study covered the period between 2015 and 2021. A structural equation model (SEM) design was used, and AMOS was utilized for data analysis. The findings of the study showed that audit committees chaired by women significantly enhanced the effectiveness of CSR committees in driving environmental innovation. This finding suggests that gender-diverse audit committee leadership can indirectly strengthen environmental innovation capabilities through better CSR governance. However, the study was limited in using innovation proxies like patent applications only.

Qaderi et al. (2023) carried out a study titled audit committee leadership attributes and CSR reporting: evidence from Jordan using data from 63 publicly listed Jordanian companies. The period covered was from 2016–2021. A panel design was used, and fixed-effects regression was conducted using EViews. The study found that female-led audit committees had a significantly higher demand for sustainability assurance and provided more in-depth CSR disclosures. This illustrates the role of leadership attributes in enhancing the credibility and depth of sustainability communications. The study did not explore industry-specific variations in its findings.

Drawing from various studies across different sectors concerning the variables employed in their studies, this study aims to address identified gaps such as the domain and regions which these studies were carried out, by incorporating women chairpersons as a moderating variable. This will be examined alongside the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting disclosure in listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study presents a clear method that was employed in order to realise the objectives of this study: An empirical study of audit committee size and sustainability reporting disclosure, moderated by audit committee women chairperson. The ex-post facto research design has, therefore, been adopted in this study because it uses data that is collected from events and activities that have occurred in the past. This design is considered the most suitable for this study. The population for this study consists of the fourteen (14) listed deposit money banks in Nigeria as at December 31, 2023. In a census sampling, the entire fourteen (14) banks were sampled over a fifteen-year time span (15 years), 2010–2024. The sampling criteria were designed to include all listed DBMs for the entire sample period, thereby eliminating any form of sampling bias.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size of the Study

S/N	Bank Name	Year of Incorporation	Year of Listing
1.	Access Bank Plc	1989	1998
2.	Ecobank Nigeria Plc	1986	2006
3.	Fidelity Bank Plc	1988	1999
4.	FirstBank of Nigeria Plc	1894	1971
5.	First City Monument Bank	1982	2004
6.	Guarantee Trust Bank Plc	1990	2007
7.	Jaiz Bank plc	2003	2015
8.	Stanbic IBTC Bank Plc	1989	1989
9.	Sterling Bank Plc	1960	1992
10.	Union Bank Plc	1917	1971
11.	United Bank for Africa Plc	1961	1970
12.	Unity Bank Plc	170	1987
13.	Wema Bank Plc	1945	1973
14.	Zentih Bank Plc	1990	2004

This study adapted the model used by Ani et al (2020) as stated below;

$$SR = \beta_0 + \beta_1Size + \beta_2Liquid + \beta_3Profit + \beta_4Meet + e \text{ ----- (1)}$$

$$SR = \beta_0 + \beta_1Size + \beta_2Liquid + \beta_3Profit + \beta_4Meet + \beta_5Size*Meet + \beta_6Liquid*Meet + \beta_7Profit*Meet + e \text{ ----- (2)}$$

Where;

SR is Sustainability Reporting

Size = Firm Size

Liquid = Liquidity

Profit = Profitability

Meet = Meeting

B₀ = intercept when the independent variables is zero

B₁- β₇ = Regression Coefficient

i = Number of Firms

t = Period of the study

e = Error term

In our study, we expunged the independent variables (Size, Liquid and Profit) used in their study as well as the moderating variable (Meeting) and replaced with our own independent variable (Audit Committee Size), control variable (Bank Size) and Women Chairpersons serving as a moderating variable. The modified regression equation of Model 1 and Model 2 in this study are therefore seen as follows:

Model 1

$$SDQI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACSZ_{it} + \beta_2 ACWC_{it} + \beta_3 BASZ_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (3)}$$

Model 2

$$SDQI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACSZ_{it} + \beta_2 ACWC_{it} + \beta_3 (ACSZ * ACWC)_{it} + \beta_4 BASZ_{it} + e_{it} \text{ ----- (4)}$$

Where;

SDQI = Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index (Dependent Variable)

ACSZ = Audit Committee Size (Independent Variable)

ACWD = Audit Committee Women Chairperson (Moderator Variable)

BASZ = Bank Size (Control Variable)

B₀ = intercept when the independent variables is zero

B₁- β₄ = Regression Coefficient

i = Number of Banks

t = Period of the study

e = Error term

Table 2: Variables Definition and Measurement

Variables	Definition	Measurement	Source(s)	Sign (+/-)
Sustainability Reporting Disclosure Quality (SDQI)	Sustainability Reporting Quality refers to the degree of completeness, accuracy, and consistency in disclosing environmental, social, and governance (ESG) information.	Measured by coding scale of three thresholds: 0 = Sustainability reports do not exist. 1 = Sustainability reports exist. 2 = Presence of Sustainability reports & sustainability committee.	Ani et al (2020)	Positive
Audit Committee Size (ACSZ)	Audit Committee Size denotes the total number of	Total number of individuals on the	Beasley et al. (2000)	Positive

	members serving on a firm's audit committee.	statutory audit committee		
Audit Committee Women Chairperson (ACWC)	Audit Committee Women Chairperson represents the gender composition of leadership within the audit committee, specifically when the chairperson is a woman.	Presence of female director in the committee = 1, Absence = 0	Aifuwa & Embele (2019), Mustafa et al. (2018)	Positive
Bank Size (BASZ)	Bank Size reflects the scale of a bank's operations and financial strength, influencing its level of public visibility and disclosure obligation.	Natural log of total assets	Chaudhry et al. (2020)	Positive

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Table 3 present the descriptive statistics for the key variables used in this study; Audit Committee Size (ACSZ), Bank Size (BASZ), Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index (SDQI) and the moderating variable: Audit Committee Women Chairperson (ACWC). It provides an overview and offer insights into key statistical measures such as the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values for the variables used in this study.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
SDQI	210	.2642857	.2209932	0	.75
ACSZ	210	5.747619	.7373294	3	9
ACWC	210	.1095238	.3130415	0	1
BASZ	210	27.4821	1.530762	23.15179	31.39923

Table 3 presented the descriptive statistics for the variables in the study which highlight notable variations in sustainability reporting practices in Nigerian deposit money banks. The SDQI (Sustainability Disclosure Quality Index) has a mean of 26.42% and a standard deviation of 22.09%, indicating moderate variability in sustainability reporting across banks ranging from a minimum of 0% to maximum of 75%. The ACSZ (Audit Committee Size) shows a mean of 5.7 with a standard deviation of 0.73, reflecting moderate variability, with committee size ranging from a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 9 members. The BASZ (Bank Size) has a mean of 27.48, with a standard deviation of 1.53, indicating a significant variation in bank sizes, with a minimum of 23.15 and a maximum of 31.40. The ACWC (Audit Committee Women Chairperson) has a low mean of 0.11 with a standard deviation of 0.31, indicating moderate variation in gender diversity across banks, where some banks have no women chairing the committee (0), while others have (1). These descriptive statistics suggest varied approaches to sustainability reporting, with areas for improvement, particularly in gender diversity and consistency in reporting.

The correlation matrix reveals the degree of relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables as shown in Table 3

Table 4: Correlation matrix

VARIABLES	SDQI	ACSZ	ACWC	BASZ
SDQI	1.0000			
ACSZ	-0.3448	1.0000		
ACWC	0.2366	-0.0248	1.0000	
BASZ	0.2869	-0.1966	0.3606	1.0000

The correlation matrix in Table 4 above reveals that there is a negative correlation between SDQI and ACSZ at -0.3448, suggesting that larger audit committees are not generally associated with higher sustainability reporting quality. However, there is a strong positive correlation between SDQI and ACWC at 0.2366 indicating that the presence of women as chairpersons in the audit committee have a notable relationship with sustainability reporting quality in these sample of banks. Similarly, BASZ also has a strong positive correlation with SDQI, this implies that larger banks tend to have more extensive and better-quality sustainability disclosures, possibly due to their greater asset base. The diagnostic test were conducted in the study to improve the validity and reliability of the statistical results. These include Normality test, multi-collinearity test, Heteroscedasticity test and Hausman specification test.

- *Normality Test*

Table 5: Shapiro-Wilk *W* test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	Z	Prob>z
SDQI	210	0.98568	2.229	1.849	0.03222
ACSZ	210	0.96453	5.521	3.941	0.00004
BASZ	210	0.99265	1.144	0.311	0.37788

The result on Table 5 shows that the data for SDQI and ACSZ does not follow normal distribution, this is due to the fact that the p-values of their Z-statistics are statistically significant at 0.03222 and 0.00004 respectively. The lack of normal distribution calls for robustness of regression technique. However, data set used for this study is normally distributed for BASZ at a p-value of 0.37788. For data set to be considered normal, the p-value have to be greater than 0.05 (Ghasemi & Zahediasl 2012).

- *Multicollinearity test*

Table 6: Multicollinearity

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	VIF	1/VIF	VIF	1/VIF
BASZ	1.20	0.834714	1.13	0.883645
ACSZ	1.24	0.804911	1.05	0.955146
ACWC	1.15	0.867736	106.50	0.009390
ACSZACWC	-	-	107.86	0.009271
Mean VIF	1.13		54.18	

The variance inflation factor (VIF) values were calculated for the independent variables for model 1 and the results shows that VIF value is below 5 and tolerance value is above 0.1, indicating no multicollinearity. However, for model 2, VIF value is way above 10 and tolerance value is less than 0.1, indicating that there is presence of multicollinearity

- **Heteroskedasticity test**

Table 7: Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Model (SDQI)	Chi ² (1)	Prob > chi ²
Model 1	3.03	0.0816
Model 2	5.67	0.0173

The Breusch-Pagan test for heteroscedasticity was conducted for both model 1 and model 2 and the result was not significant (p-value > 0.05) for model 1 indicating no presence of heteroscedasticity in the data. However, it was significant for model 2, indicating the presence of heteroscedasticity.

- **Hausman Specification test**

The hausman specification test was conducted in order to determine whether the fixed effect model or the random effect model is most appropriate for the study and the difference in coefficient was significant (Prob > chi²=0.000). This indicate that the fixed effect model is most appropriate.

Table 8: Hausman Specification test

Chi ² (4)	Prob > chi ²
31.64	0.000

- **Regression Result**

Table 9: Regression Result

Variables	Model 1 (Pooled OLS)			Model 2 (Fixed Effect)		
	Coef.	t	p>t	Coef.	t	p>t
SDQI						
ACSZ	-.0923573	-4.82	0.000	-.0620087	-3.71	0.000
ACWC	.1196098	2.52	0.012	-.1560053	-0.44	0.662
BASZ	.0238479	2.41	0.017	.0667098	5.61	0.000
ACSZACWC	-	-	-	.049546	0.77	0.440
_cons	.1266304	0.41	0.685	-1.226457	-3.50	0.001
F-Statistics (Prob)	16.50(0.0000)			14.99(0.0000)		
R²	0.1937			0.2380		
Adjusted R²	0.1820			0.1489		

Model 1 examines the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria as presented in Table 9. The result from the regression model revealed that the R² stands at 0.1937, indicating that approximately 19.37% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R² of 0.1820 suggests that approximately 18.20% of the variance is explained after adjusting for model complexity. Furthermore, the Prob (F-statistic) of 0.0000 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant at the 1% level.

The coefficient of -0.0923573, t-value of -4.82, and p-value of 0.000 suggest that the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting is negative but statistically significant. This implies that changes in audit committee size of deposit money banks in Nigeria significantly influence sustainability reporting. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that audit committee size does not have a significant effect on sustainability reporting, is hereby rejected. This result is in line with studies carried out by Buallay and Al-Ajmi (2020), Meo, et al. (2024) and Waseem, et al. (2024) who all found audit committee size to be significantly related with sustainability reporting. However, the result is in contrast with Hendrati et al. (2023) whose result revealed that audit committee size has an inverse relationship with sustainability reporting.

Similarly, the coefficient of 0.1196098, t-value of 2.52, and p-value of 0.012 show that audit committee women chairperson has a positive and significant effect on sustainability reporting. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis, which states that audit committee women chairperson has no significant effect on sustainability reporting. This result supports previous studies conducted by Zampone et al. (2024), Almonte (2025) and Qaderi et al. (2023) who all found audit committee women chairperson to significantly affect sustainability reporting disclosure. This result however, does not support previous studies carried out by Nishii and Mayer (2009) which found gender of audit committee chairs alone did not directly correlate with improved sustainability reporting.

Model 2 examines the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson on the effect of audit committee size and sustainability reporting of deposit money bank in Nigeria. The result from the fixed effect regression model revealed that the R^2 stands at 0.2380, indicating that approximately 23.8% of the variance in the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables in the model. The adjusted R^2 of 0.1489 suggests that approximately 14.89% of the variance is explained after adjusting for model complexity. Furthermore, the Prob (F-statistic) of 0.0000 indicates that the overall model is statistically significant at the 1% level.

The moderating role of audit committee women chairperson on the effect of audit committee size and sustainability reporting of deposit money bank in Nigeria shows that ACSZACWC has a coefficient of 0.049546, with t-values of 0.77 and p-values of 0.440 which is insignificant. Thus, we fail to reject the null hypotheses which states that audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate audit committee size and sustainability reporting disclosure of deposit money banks in Nigeria. This result shows that audit committee women chairperson as a moderating variable is an insignificant factor in the sustainability reporting disclosure of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria.

While there is strong evidence supporting the beneficial role of audit committee women chairperson in improving sustainability reporting (Zampone et al. 2024; Almonte, 2025 & Qaderi et al. 2023), the moderating role effect may be insignificant or weakened by organizational, industry or regulatory factors. More research is needed to identify contextual factors that enhance or limit the effectiveness of female leadership in audit committees on sustainability reporting.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting and the moderating role of audit committee women chairperson in Nigerian deposit money banks from 2010 to 2024. The result of the multiple regression analysis revealed that audit committee size has a significant effect on sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria. However, findings also revealed that audit committee women chairperson does not significantly affect sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Similarly, findings also revealed that audit

committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate the relationship between audit committee size and sustainability reporting of deposit money banks in Nigeria.

Based on the findings from this study, it is recommended that larger audit committee are better positioned to enhance the quality of sustainability reporting. Banks in Nigeria should consider increasing the size of their audit committees by including members with diverse expertise, particularly those with backgrounds in sustainability reporting. Consequently, while gender diversity on audit committee is important for improving sustainability reporting, the study revealed that audit committee women chairperson does not significantly moderate the effect of audit committee size on sustainability reporting. This could suggest that other factors such as expertise, experience or regulatory pressure might play a more significant role in shaping sustainability disclosure. Banks should therefore continue to encourage gender diversity within audit committees, but without overemphasizing the role of female chairperson. Instead, more focused should be placed on enhancing the overall competence and diversity (in terms of skills, expertise and knowledge of sustainability) of the entire committee.

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